

UDC 343.9

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Problems of Crime Prevention in the Field of Business

У даній публікації йде мова про проблеми запобігання злочинності у сфері господарювання. Проблеми запобігання посилюються впливом війни на злочинність, також, аналізується статистика вчинення господарських кримінальних правопорушень. Вказується, що статистична тенденція до зниження розпочалась ще задовго до початку війни, тож необхідно враховувати нові прояви злочинності у зазначеній сфері. Зазначено, не лише про воєнні, а й політичні, економічні, соціальні, демографічні, соціально–психологічні, кримінально-ситуаційні фактори, фактори фонових явищ злочинності та інші криміногенні фактори, що позитивно чи негативно вплинули на стан злочинності у сфері господарської діяльності, у сфері економіки та управління економічними процесами, взагалі. У статті звертається увага, що подальше формування ефективної системи запобігання кримінальним правопорушенням в Україні виникають проблеми без отримання достовірних статистичних показників та використання отриманих даних стану злочинності щодо узагальнення даних та планування заходів запобігання на майбутнє. Акцентується увага на тому, що важливість такої діяльності пов'язана, насамперед, з взаємопов'язаними криміногенними факторами які виявила саме війна. Це призводить до змінення показників злочинності у державі з часів початку повномасштабної війни і до тепер. Взаємопов'язані фактори злочинності виявлені війною зумовлюють, нажаль, зростання рівня саме латентної злочинності, безкарності винних у вчиненні кримінальних правопорушень у сфері господарювання та об'єктивна неможливість правоохоронних органів у період війни ефективно виконувати функціональні обов'язки. Чим і користуються злочинці. Також розглядається питання, що різка тенденція до зниження кількості виявлених кримінальних правопорушень у сфері господарської діяльності свідчить, що існуючі статистичні дані, відносно природно-латентних кримінальних правопорушень, не можуть бути об'єктивним засобом визначення реального стану злочинності у сфері господарської діяльності. Відповідно, можуть виникати ідеї про необхідність розробити опосередковані, не прямі методи визначення реального стану вчинення природно-латентних кримінальних правопорушень у сфері господарської діяльності. Вважається, що число вчинення таких кримінальних правопорушень у досліджуваній сфері є децю вищим ніж у офіційній статистиці.

Ключові слова: покарання, кримінальні правопорушення, проблеми запобігання, господарська діяльність, правоохоронні органи, умови злочинності, латентність, економічна безпека, військова агресія.

This publication deals with the problems of crime prevention in the field of business. The problems of prevention are aggravated by the impact of the war on crime, and the statistics of the commission of economic criminal offenses are also analyzed. It is indicated that the statistical downward trend began long before the start of the war, so it is necessary to take into account new manifestations of crime in the specified area. Not only military, but also political, economic, social, demographic, socio-psychological, criminal-situational factors, factors of background phenomena of crime and other criminogenic factors that positively or negatively affected the state of crime in the sphere of economic activity, in the sphere of economy and management of economic processes, in general. The article draws attention to the fact that the further formation of an effective system for the prevention of criminal offenses in Ukraine has problems without obtaining reliable statistical indicators and using the received data on the state of crime in order to generalize data and plan preventive measures for the future. Attention is focused on the fact that the importance of such activity is connected, first of all, with interrelated criminogenic factors that the war itself revealed. This leads to a change in crime rates in the state from the beginning of the full-scale war until now. Interrelated factors of crime revealed by the war lead,

unfortunately, to an increase in the level of latent crime, impunity for those guilty of criminal offenses in the economic sphere, and the objective inability of law enforcement agencies to effectively perform their functional duties during the war. What criminals use. The question is also considered that the sharp tendency to decrease the number of detected criminal offenses in the field of economic activity shows that the existing statistical data, relative to natural latent criminal offenses, cannot be an objective means of determining the real state of criminality in the field of economic activity. Accordingly, ideas may arise about the need to develop indirect, not direct methods of determining the real state of commission of naturally latent criminal offenses in the field of economic activity. It is believed that the number of such criminal offenses in the studied area is somewhat higher than in official statistics.

Keywords: *punishment, criminal offences, prevention problems, economic activity, law enforcement agencies, crime conditions, latency, economic security, military aggression.*

Formulation of the problem. The problem of crime in the sphere of economic activity is of great practical importance in combating crime in general. A comprehensive study of this legal phenomenon not only from the point of view of criminal law, but also of criminology involves the study of modern problems of crime in the field of economic activity generated by war.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Issues of crime problems from the standpoint of various sciences of the criminal law cycle were previously considered by such domestic and foreign specialists as: Yu. Antonyan, V. Holina, P. Dagel, I. Danshin, A. Dolgova, O. Dzhuzha, V. Dryomin, M. Dunas, A. Zakaliuk, A. Zadorozhny, V. Kudryavtsev, N. Kuznetsova, G. Kulyk, M. Klinard, H. Kaiser, N. Leykina, H. Minkovsky, C. Lombroso, V. Luneev, I. Noy, V. Sysoev, P. Schneider and others. Separate criminal-legal aspects related to crimes committed in the sphere of economic activity are partially investigated in the works of A. Smirnova "Criminological problems of crime prevention in the sphere of business activity" (2002), O. Kalman "Crime in the sphere of the economy of Ukraine : theoretical and applied problems of prevention" (2004), O. Tytarenko "Problems of combating economic crimes in the coal industry" (2006), Yu. Levchenko "Prevention of crimes committed in the oil and gas complex of Ukraine" (2008), V. Stavinskyi "Criminological characteristics and prevention of crimes in the oil and gas complex" (2012), A. Zadorozhny "Crime prevention in the field of official activity" (2013), O. Busol "Combating corruption crime in Ukraine in the context of the modern anti-corruption strategy" (2015).

Problems not solved before. Usually, the attention of some researchers focuses on certain aspects of the prevention of economic crimes, they

concentrate their efforts mainly on the criminal-legal aspects of the problem (determine the components of each crime that characterize crimes in the field of economic activity). Other researchers focus on the person of the criminal, on the problematic aspects of the criminological characteristics of corruption crime and the definition of effective mechanisms for combating it, and cannot fully reveal the specifics of official crime in the field of economic activity as a complex socio-legal phenomenon. In addition, scientific research into the causes and conditions affecting the commission of crimes in the field of economic activity did not exhaust the range of existing theoretical problems of preventing crimes in the field of economic activity, and some of their provisions require further development taking into account the provisions of martial law in the state.

The purpose of the article. To investigate the problems of criminality in the sphere of economic activity, as well as the regularity of modern reasons and conditions that contribute to the commission of a crime during the war, distinguishing it among themselves in order to ensure the improvement of the effectiveness of activities aimed at preventing crime in Ukraine.

Presenting main material. Currently, one of the main vectors of such activity is the elimination of causes, conditions and other factors that generate criminal manifestations and contribute to their development. It is worth noting that crime prevention is a complex activity that is provided by state bodies, the public and by attracting international assistance. This is the task not only of state institutions, but also of the public. The main principles of crime prevention are primarily based on the regulatory and legal basis of the internal and external policy of the state, which includes the criminological policy, which determines the theoretical foundations, directions, goals, and mechanisms of preventive

influence on crime. As practice shows, modern initiatives of the state's criminological policy, the introduction of new mechanisms to prevent crime in general and in the field of business are of particular importance today. It is worth noting that the Constitution of Ukraine stipulates that the need of a society that builds a rule of law is to ensure the prevention of crime.

Analyzing the state of crime in the business sphere, it is worth paying attention to the dynamics of official statistics.

As noted below, crime in the field of economic activity before the Russian aggression in 2013–2021 decreased by half. This indicates a certain stability in the state, the transparency of business and the effectiveness of the law enforcement system. Or that it is the creation of favorable conditions for reducing the number of committed criminal offenses in the specified area. So, the statistics reflecting the state of detection of economic crimes in Ukraine over the last decade really show a certain stabilization. In particular, according to the official data of the Prosecutor General's Office: in 2013, 11,104 criminal offenses were detected in the field of economic activity, in 2014 - 8,418 kr. pr., in 2015 - 7,631 kr. pr., in 2016 - 6,940 kr. pr., in 2017 - 6,297 kr. pr., in 2018 - 6334 kr. pr., in 2019 - 5,947 kr. pr., 2020 - 5342 kr. pr., in 2021 - 5,469 kr. pr., of which there are 5,350 crimes and 119 criminal misdemeanors [1].

At present, it is impossible to talk about the result of the influence of the war on the criminal world to such an extent that it simply refused to commit economic criminal offenses. Unfortunately, this is not the case, since the above-mentioned statistical trend began long before the start of the war, i.e., even in previous periods before the above-mentioned statistical data. In general, we can talk not only about military, but also political, economic, social, demographic, socio-psychological, criminal-situational factors [2], factors of the background phenomena of crime and other criminogenic factors that positively or negatively affected the state of crime in the sphere economic activity, the sphere of economy and management of economic processes, in general [3, p. 374–376].

It is worth noting that the further formation of an effective system for the prevention of criminal offenses in Ukraine is complicated without obtaining reliable statistical indicators and using the received data on the state of crime in order to generalize data

and plan prevention measures for the future. The importance of such activity is primarily related to interrelated criminogenic factors. First of all, there is a war in Ukraine. This leads to a change in crime rates in the state from the beginning of the full-scale war until now. This is accompanied by both positive and negative changes in the law enforcement system and our society as a whole. Negative changes are caused, unfortunately, by the growth of the level of latent crime, impunity for those guilty of criminal offenses in the economic sphere, and the objective inability of law enforcement agencies to effectively perform their duties to prevent crime during the war. What criminals use.

A sharp tendency to decrease the number of detected criminal offenses in the field of economic activity shows that the existing statistical data regarding naturally latent criminal offenses cannot be an objective means of determining the real state of crime in the field of economic activity. Accordingly, ideas may arise about the need to develop indirect, not direct methods of determining the real state of commission of naturally latent criminal offenses in the field of economic activity. It is considered somewhat superfluous, since it is obvious that the number of such criminal offenses in the researched area is definitely higher [3, p. 181–183].

The following can be considered important, how to increase the effectiveness of measures to detect, prevent and counter the commission of latent crime. Since the determination of the very real state of the commission of such criminal offenses cannot affect the state of their detection, prevention and countermeasures, it is obvious that all efforts should be directed to the determination and elimination of the real reasons that lead to the commission of these criminal offenses, as well as the determination and elimination of the causes that created the problems of detection, prevention and counteraction of the commission of latent crime in the sphere of economy, in general, and the sphere of economic activity, in particular [3, p. 150–153].

Meanwhile, it should be noted that many experts do not see the difference between the detection of obvious criminal offenses that are capable of manifesting themselves in some way, and the detection of non-obvious, latent, incapable of self-manifesting criminal offenses [4].

Therefore, it is worth understanding that today it is somewhat difficult to obtain qualitative

indicators of crime in the field of economic activity. Yes, when committing obvious criminal offenses capable of self-manifestation, this is normal. The fact of committing such criminal offenses is obvious, they manifest themselves as a result of, for example, conducting an audit of economic activity. Offenses are immediately registered and criminal proceedings are initiated.

In connection with large-scale military operations and the loss of control over part of the territory, the country daily suffers great human and material losses, which leads to the degradation of the economy and the social sphere. According to the results of the analysis conducted within the framework of the "Russia will pay" project, the experts of the Kyiv School of Economics cited the total losses of the state's economy. The total losses of the Ukrainian economy, taking into account both direct losses and indirect losses (reduction of GDP, termination of investments, outflow of labor, additional costs for defense and social support, etc.), range from \$564 billion to \$600 billion [5].

According to the operational assessment of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, real GDP in the first quarter of 2022 decreased by 19.3% compared to the previous quarter (taking into account the seasonal factor), and by 15.1% compared to the first quarter of 2021 [6]. According to preliminary forecasts, losses due to the war are expected to be very significant. Real GDP may decrease by at least a third in the coming years [7].

This problem can be analyzed from another side. Currently, there is a need to make changes and additions, taking into account the state of war, to the Comprehensive Crime Prevention Program until 2025. Such a program should take into account the likely increase in the level of criminalization during the war, the ability of the state and society to implement effective measures to prevent any crimes, miscalculations and shortcomings of previous activities regarding its provision and implementation practice.

Next, the country's industrial sector will experience significant losses. Thus, after the beginning of the military invasion of Russia, about 30% of Ukrainian companies stopped their activities, and 45% worked with reduced capacity. In the second quarter of 2022, the number of enterprises that completely stopped their activities almost halved compared to the beginning of hostilities (from 32% to 17%). However, 60% of enterprises operate below

the pre-war level of employment, almost 23% - more than twice as much. According to a survey conducted by the European Business Association among representatives of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), the number of non-working enterprises has decreased from 42% to 26%. 17% of SMEs have already resumed work, another 23% are preparing to resume, and the number of entrepreneurs working full-time has also increased - from 13% to 20% (among large companies - 41%, according to AmCham) [8].

Also, in accordance with the Enterprise Relocation Program, which the Government will implement from mid-March 2022 with the aim of maintaining the stability of the Ukrainian economy by moving enterprises from territories close to or in the war zone to safer regions of Western Ukraine, by the beginning of June 2022 more than 600 enterprises that participated in this program have already completed their relocation, 390 of them have resumed their work at new sites in 88 western regions of Ukraine. Another 87 enterprises are at various stages of transportation, 151 enterprises are drawing up the necessary documents [9].

So, as we can see, the above indicators are only a small part of those reformatting of the business sector and losses that the Ukrainian economy is experiencing as a result of the war, which in turn will negatively affect both the socio-economic situation in the country and crime in the future in this area. As a result of the destabilization of normal economic activity, part of the adult population became unemployed. And even despite the gradual recovery of some enterprises, unfortunately there is a tendency to increase the number of unemployed and impoverish the population, which may intensify in the near future. All of these negative trends are exacerbated by the large-scale military invasion of Russia and may further lead to an increase in the criminal situation in the country as a whole.

Therefore, the question arises already today regarding the formation of a policy in the field of crime prevention, especially in the field of economy, as the main strategy of the internal policy of the Ukrainian state, which determines the main directions, goals, ways of influencing crime through the formation of criminal, criminal procedural and criminal enforcement legislation, regulation the practice of their application, as well as the development and implementation of measures aimed

at preventing criminal offenses [3, p.26], including in the field of business.

Already today in Ukraine, the mass media are reporting that basic approaches to understanding the content of crime prevention as a whole have been developed, conditions have been created for the development of its doctrine and legislative concept of implementation. The theory of criminal legal policy in Ukraine received sufficient development, which made it possible to form its doctrine. The development of its theoretical foundations in separate areas, the analysis of a number of private problems is being carried out. This opens up opportunities for the development and adoption at the legislative level of the concept of the criminal law policy of Ukraine for the medium-term perspective [10, p.19].

Although this also causes some doubt among scientists. In their opinion, it is necessary to develop such principles of prevention, which will be used more effectively during the practical activities of specialized law enforcement agencies of Ukraine.

It is worth agreeing that among the primary tasks of the state is the exposure of organized criminal groups and the cessation of their actions, increasing the effectiveness of the fight against conspiratorial criminal communities that use international conflicts associated with the "shadow" economy, as well as with criminal groups abroad [11].

Conclusions. As you can see, the solution to the related problems is not limited to activities aimed at identifying and neutralizing criminal manifestations and reducing the level of crime in any area. Currently, it is not possible to prevent only a certain type of crime by influencing various objective and subjective circumstances, which in any case provoke criminal behavior. It is necessary to carry out gradual persistent activity of the state to prevent crimes, if necessary limiting human rights and freedoms, developing effective mechanisms for crime prevention and protection of the state's security as a whole.

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